

THE EFFECTS OF MIRAA ON DISCIPLINE MANAGEMENT AMONG STUDENTS IN DAY SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN TIGANIA EAST DISTRICT, MERU COUNTY, KENYA

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Abstract:

Discipline remains the single most common and pernicious problem that educators face in their day-to-day teaching. Drug abuse among the students in schools leads to high level indiscipline and the consequences are strikes, violence, rape, disobedience to authority and damage of school property. Miraa chewing has of late been a major source of indiscipline in secondary schools in Tigania East District. Unfortunately, many well-meaning parents, the clergy and teachers do not see the problem of miraa chewing yet it has far reaching effects on the management of discipline in schools. In light of this the main purpose of this study was to investigate the effects of miraa chewing amongst students on discipline management in day secondary schools in Tigania East District and make necessary recommendations. The study looked at the effects of miraa chewing on discipline management, cases related to miraa chewing among students, measures employed by school management to curb drug menace and if there is effective drug policy in day secondary schools in Tigania East District and identify strategies that could be used by school management to address miraa menace. The study adopted descriptive survey design. Simple random sampling was used to select 10 schools out of 26 day schools for this study. Since the study involved boys in day secondary schools in Tigania East District because the social cultural setting does not allow girls to chew miraa, the method was appropriate as it gave equal probability of the population to be selected. Questionnaires were administered to guidance and counseling teachers, students and interview schedules to principals of sampled schools. Closed-ended and open-ended questions were used to give an opportunity to respondents to express their views. Collected data was analyzed and presented in form of frequency distribution tables, graphs, pie charts and percentages. The analysis showed that miraa chewing by students has varied effects on discipline management in

day schools, and further revealed that though there are drug policies in schools, the school administration was not doing enough to enforce the policy. The study recommends for training of more guidance and counseling teachers to be able to guide students to change to desired behavior.

Keywords: indiscipline, drug abuse, chewing, menace, miraa, guidance, counseling

1. Introduction

The history of the human race has also been the history of drug abuse. Over the years the use of illegal drugs in schools and in the entire society has spread at an alarming rate and has reached almost every part of the world. Kiiru (2004) classifies miraa as a drug and observes that miraa, alcohol and bhang have had significant effects on discipline management in secondary schools. He asserts that miraa, alcohol, bhang and tobacco are the mainly abused drugs by students ranging from very young ages in primary schools up to the university. Since several parents have lost control over their children, and, freed from parental control, a very big percentage of students in secondary schools have succumbed to drugs and substance abuse.

This has made discipline to be elusive in secondary schools and though most of the principals are well trained and have theoretical skills required of a leader, they are still faced with challenging cases of indiscipline among student in secondary schools. In our secondary schools majority of the students who engage in drug abuse are between ages 14 to 19. Discipline in schools has deteriorated terribly due to drug abuse. Discipline is paramount in school organization in order to achieve the set goals and objective. Kombo (2005) points out that discipline is very important for effective learning and unless it is enforced the learning Institutions cannot achieve their set goals and objectives. Majority of youngsters in most countries, schools included engage in drug abuse from early ages.

According to a United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) report, (2005) some 200 million people or 5% of the total world's population aged 15-64 have used drugs at least once. Drug abuse has increased over the years throughout the world.

A report by United Nations Drug Control Programme (2004) estimates that 3.3 to 4.1% of global population consumes drugs, but more worrying is that according to the report those hooked to drugs are the young ones in schools e.g. in Pakistan majority of drug abusers are between age 15-20. In Czech Republic, the report shows that 37% of drug users are between 15-17 years old.

Kenya youth engages in drug taking. These includes; alcohol, smoking bhang and miraa chewing. According to the Ministerial Council on Drug Strategy (2005), drug abuse including smoking, drinking alcohol, Miraa chewing and bhang are rampant among the youth. The issue of drug abuse by students has complicated discipline management in secondary schools. Students who engage in these drugs hardly remain in class because they keep on sneaking out of school thus compromising their studies. Gachigua (2005) noted that discipline remains the single most common and pernicious problem that educators face in their day-to-day teaching. In Kenyan schools, strikes and riots are some of the common features of indiscipline. In most secondary schools, principals have delegated issues of discipline to deputies, senior teachers, guidance and counseling masters thus creating a loop hole in the management of discipline. Makewa in East African Standard July 28th (2001) blamed indiscipline on drug abuse and poor management in secondary schools.

For years, drugs have been in use by students in secondary schools thus causing havoc to discipline management. Kombo (2005), points out that in the contemporary society, drug use has always been used by students within learning institutions. Not only is there a significant rise in the number of students that turn to drugs as a means to escape from problems of life and challenges of education, but drug abuse has also been associated with escalating strikes, truancy and dropout cases in secondary schools. Miraa chewing is one of the commonly abused drugs by the students leading to truancy in learning institutions. The Report by National Baseline (2002) on drugs and substance among the Kenyan Youth found Miraa to be one of the drugs abused by the Kenyan youth, as shown in the table below.

Table 1: Preference of drug abuse

Institution	Alcohol	Tobacco	Bhagn	Miraa	Inhale
Primary	22.7	2.2	2.2	1.6	2.1
Secondary	43.8	6.2	6.2	7.1	8.2
University	68.5	10.2	10.2	7.6	5.6
Polytechnics	60.1	11	11	11	4.7
Other Institutions	47.1	9.3	8.5	21.8	4.7

Source: National Baseline on drugs, Kenya 2002

When students chew miraa, they cannot concentrate in class, are absent minded with red eyes, keeps yawning, are shaggy and look fatigued. The Report of the National Council for Science and Technology (1996), on miraa asserts that, once students chew miraa they complain of stomach upsets, neglects personal hygiene, look fatigued and develop antagonistic attitude to all forms of authority.

The perspective the society has towards miraa chewing particularly among the Meru community and peer influence has driven majority of youth to miraa chewing. Kombo (2005), points out that the factors contributing to increase in drug abuse within learning institutions includes; peer pressure, ignorance, break down of family unit, easy accessibility of drugs and laxity in institutions management.

Lack of research that examines the effects of miraa chewing among students in secondary schools is of great concern, thus necessitating investigations on the effects of miraa chewing on discipline management in day secondary schools in Tigania East District and suggests ways of curbing the menace which is so rampant in secondary schools in the district.

2. Statement of the Problem

Drugs and substance abuse for example, alcohol, bhang, miraa and tobacco has many negative consequences within the abuser. Some of these consequences are biological, psychological, sociological and even legal. Such complexity demands a clear understanding of the student's perception on drugs and substance abuse. After the ban on the use of corporal punishment by the government in 2001, school principals were left with only one option of guidance and counseling as a tool to change errant behaviour in students. Miraa chewing among students in secondary schools in Tigania East District is a major cause of indiscipline because students boycott classes to engage in miraa harvesting and chewing. They fail to do class assignments hence resulting to conflict with teachers. They sneak out of school and are hostile to authority resulting to expulsion from school. As the problem becomes of great concern, research on the effects of miraa on discipline management in day secondary schools in Tigania East District was necessary to help with the solution of stamping out the menace and sensitize the stakeholders on its effects to students.

2.1 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to find out the effects of miraa chewing by students on discipline management in day secondary schools in Tigania East District and make the necessary recommendations.

2.2 Objectives of the Study

1. To find out the effects of miraa chewing by students on discipline management in day secondary schools in Tigania East District.

2. To investigate indiscipline cases related to miraa chewing among students in day secondary schools in Tigania East District.
3. To find out measures employed by school management to curb miraa chewing menace in day secondary schools in Tigania East District.
4. To find out the effectiveness of drug policies in day secondary schools in Tigania East District.
5. To identify strategies that could be used by school management to address miraa menace in day secondary schools in Tigania East District.

2.3 Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions.

1. What are the effects of miraa chewing among students on discipline management in day secondary schools?
2. What indiscipline cases result from miraa chewing among students?
3. How does the school administration deal with cases of indiscipline related to miraa chewing among students?
4. Are there effective policy guidelines on drugs in day secondary school in Tigania East District?
5. What measure should day secondary schools institute to curb miraa menace in Tigania East District?

2.4 Significance of the Study

Kenya, like many other developing countries is faced with the social problem of high rates of drug abuse among the youth. The percentage of drug abusers in secondary schools is increasing despite the efforts to eradicate the problem. According to NACADA (2008), alcohol, miraa, tobacco and bhang have seriously affected discipline in secondary schools. Since this study focuses on miraa chewing among students and its effects on discipline management, the findings of the study will have both theoretical and practical implications on the administration of discipline in secondary schools in Tigania East District and other schools in Kenya with related cases.

Theoretically, the study will contribute to the advancement of knowledge about the specific effects of miraa chewing among students leading to indiscipline in day secondary schools in Tigania East District. Practically, the study will generate strategies of dealing with indiscipline cases related to miraa chewing to the school managements and it will benefit the Ministry of Education to come up with policy guidelines on miraa chewing among students in secondary schools in Kenya.

2.5 Theoretical Framework

The study was based on Behaviour Modification Theory by Watson (1924). Behaviour Modification Theory is a technique of application of principles of learning in the promotion of desired changes. The Theory argues that people have learned to be the way they are. People have learned responses that cause problems and can change them or relearn more appropriate responses.

A problem learned can also be relearned. The Theory further asserts that Behaviorists use three general procedures; identification of the problem and frequencies, treatment of the maladaptive behaviour and observation to assess whether there has been a behaviour change.

In secondary schools, students learn different behaviours from peers, teachers, parents and the community. Some students learn bad behaviours and become maladaptive while Modification Theory, where several principles of behavior modification such as; positive reinforcement, punishment, shaping, social reinforcement, shaping and expulsion can be applied to students who chew miraa so that they can relearn and discard the bad behaviour of miraa chewing which leads to indiscipline.

2.6 Conceptual Framework

Students' behaviour in our schools is influenced by drugs, peer pressure, society, laxity of parents or laxity of administration and teachers among others. This leads to deviant students who become truant, disobey authority, initiate others to strike, are always absent from school, perform poorly in exams and eventually drop out of school. Therefore, the school should apply behavioural modification principles of guidance and counseling, positive/negative reinforcement, punishment and expulsions to curb the problems.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework showing influence of drugs and its effects

Source: Author's conceptualization

3. Literature Review

3.1 Concept of School Discipline

School discipline is the system of rules, punishments and behavioral strategies appropriate to the regulation of students and the maintenance of order in schools. The sole aim of discipline is to control the student's actions and behaviour. There can be no order in any school unless clear rules and regulations are established to enforce discipline among students. A high level of discipline must be established if the school has to achieve its goals and objectives. Kombo (2005) agrees that discipline is very important for effective learning and if not enforced by schools, they cannot achieve their set goals and objectives. Etisi(2007),notes that for a school to achieve its goals and objectives, school discipline should aim at modeling the behaviour of students to have valuable social skills that promote success in school and future life.

Okumbe (1998) distinguishes two ways of maintaining discipline in schools. He singled out two types of discipline maintenance namely; preventive and corrective discipline. Preventive discipline is that which aims at taking precautionary measures to

encourage the students to follow standards, rules and regulations through guidance or clarifying rules and regulations to students. Corrective on the other hand, aims at providing remedial or curative measures to undisciplined students and may take the form of punishment, scolding, seclusion or counseling. Okumbe, (1998) agrees that school discipline should aim at modifying students' faulty behaviour and discourage others from involvement in undesirable behaviours.

Therefore, this means that once the faulty behaviour is corrected at high levels among students, desired discipline is maintained thus the school is able to achieve its goals and objectives.

3.2 Other Common Drugs Affecting School Discipline

Over the past years, the use of drugs in schools has been alarming. The society has viewed schools as fertile grounds for business thus different drugs are available within the school environs. These include:

i. Alcohol

Alcohol has been and is still used in both traditional and modern society. Due to modern civilization, parents drink and keep alcohol in their homes thus it is easily accessible by their children. The media has complicated the matter since alcohol is freely advertised showing portraits of people drinking and having a great time thus influencing the youth into drinking. Since alcohol is readily available in our school, environs students in day schools engage in drinking and come to school when drunk. This has affected discipline management in day secondary schools because when students get drunk they tend to be violent, merry and too talkative thus disrupting the normal school routine.

ii. Smoking

Tobacco can be smoked, snorted or chewed. The society in the modern world has embraced smoking without caution thus influencing the youth into smoking. The media advertises associate popular sports idols and other stars with smoking. Parents send their children to buy cigarettes and smoke in their presence thus aping them. Students who smoke rarely stay in class, don't observe cleanliness and are absent minded. They often sneak out of school to buy and smoke cigarettes. This has seriously affected discipline management in secondary schools.

iii. Bhang

In modern Kenya, bhang has been a lucrative business. Bhang handlers target schools and other institutions of learning. Majority of secondary school students take bhang which is readily available within the school environment. After smoking, they are always in merry mood, develop don't care attitudes and defies school authorities. This

has compromised discipline management leading to unrest in most schools. The report by National Council of Churches in Kenya (1992) linked students' indiscipline with alcohol abuse. Mwana „a“ Nzeki (1999), agrees that most Kenyan schools have continued to report serious indiscipline cases such as killings, burning of school buildings and rape due to the influence of alcohol and drugs.

The Report of Presidential Committee on students unrest and indiscipline in Kenyan secondary schools (1991) established that students indiscipline emanates from alcohol abuse and other drugs since the student under the influence of drugs becomes unreasonable and violent because drugs gives the abuser false sense of greatness and power, thus leading to wanton destruction of school property.

Currently, drug abuse is so alarming especially alcohol abuse among the students in secondary schools. With the introduction of day schools by the government, most students come to school when drunk. In most parts of the Kenya, alcohol is readily available either in kiosks, bars or the environs to students and the society seems less bothered with this menace.

Andrew Otieno and A. Avo (2009), carried out a study on drug abuse in Kisumu where nine random schools were selected. The finding shows that most students take alcohol. It further reports that 400,000 students in secondary schools take alcohol leading to massive indiscipline. The study further reveals that a large number of students in schools use tobacco (smoking) miraa, glue sniffing and bhang. On the other hand, smoking is posing a big threat to school discipline. In schools, smokers may be found in odd places at odd hours of the day especially on the toilets smoking. They can't concentrate in class.

A Report by the Global Tobacco Youth Survey – Kenya (2006) reveals that 13% (400,000) of all school children in Kenya smoke cigarettes, a habit which to some starts as early as 7 years old. This leads to indiscipline because the students keep on sneaking out of school to smoke or even steal other student's items to sell in order to get money to buy cigarettes.

The media has complicated the issue by airing adverts linking smoking with being “cool” thus impacting negatively on students. Bhang is also common in most schools. Most of the society members view the school as a fertile place for business hence peddles drugs like bhang to students.

According to World Health Report (2006), Kenya has been noted as one of the developing countries in Africa that has lately been experiencing rapid increase in production, distribution and consumption of bhang. Students are among the consumers of this drug in Kenyan schools as revealed by National Baseline on Drugs (2002).

Other drugs such as heroin cocaine and madrax are used in few school especially those in towns like Mombasa, Nairobi and Kisumu. Kaguthi, NACADA director (2008) asserts that the use of alcohol, smoking and other forms of drugs among students emanates from break – down in family values. Most parents smoke in front of their children and take alcohol with them and some help their parents in selling cigarettes and alcohol. This influences them to take the drugs.

3.3 Miraa as a Drug

The report by National Baseline on Drugs (2002) reveals that miraa is one of the drug abused by students in secondary schools. In all the researches, information is lacking on its effects on students discipline in schools.

Thus, the researcher wants to find out the effects of miraa chewing amongst students in day secondary schools in Tigania East District on discipline management in schools since the drug is rampantly used in schools and has led to several indiscipline cases.

In traditional Meru community miraa chewing was a preserve of the elderly men. Today this is not the case because it is chewed by both the old and the young ones. Students even carry miraa to school thus; it is of great concern to the researcher since it contributes to school indiscipline.

In Meru community miraa chewing is viewed as having milder effects on the health lives of the users than that of alcohol and smoking. This is ignorance and lack of knowledge on the effects of miraa to the health of the user because after chewing miraa one becomes absent minded and cannot concentrate, does not observe cleanliness, looks fatigued and retortive. Several researches which have been carried out looks at the effect of miraa on health of the user but none has looked at the effect of miraa chewing on discipline issues among secondary school students.

This is the gap the researcher intends to fill and bring awareness of its effects on discipline management in day secondary schools in Tigania East District. Several researches show the effects of miraa. NACADA (2010), on miraa abuse by the Kenyan youth enumerated the following effects of miraa to the chewer;

- i. Upon chewing miraa one experiences an unusual feeling of excitement and tends to talk too much, loses concentration on simple tasks or even forgets simple facts.
- ii. Chewing miraa causes rapid heart rate and increased blood pressure.
- iii. There is effect on libido and less sexual prowess due inability to attain and sustain an erection, thus the individual is withdrawn and suffers from insomnia.

- iv. Miraa chewing suppresses appetite leading to poor health; chewer's neglect personal hygiene, complains of stomach upsets and leads to aggression and antagonistic attitude to all forms of authority.
- v. The active ingredients in miraa (Cathine and Cathinone) make the body of the chewer to produce excessive amounts of sperm without one being sexually active thus oozing out uncontrollably.

According to Wikipedia and Capital FM (2011), the following are effects of miraa;

- i. Miraa induces mild euphoria and excitement to the chewer.
- ii. Causes drowsiness and hallucinations.
- iii. Leads to loss of appetite.
- iv. Users neglect their families.
- v. Continued use of miraa leads to anorexia thus causing malnutrition and increased susceptibility to infectious diseases.

Consequently, on the positive, miraa acts as the main source of income to many families in Meru community and other parts which grow the crop. It also provides employment thus looked upon as a source of livelihood. As a result, the society in general and the clergy do not speak against miraa chewing, it has compromised discipline in schools in Tigania East District since students engage in miraa chewing without fear. The researcher endeavours to find out the effects of miraa chewing on discipline management problems in day secondary schools in Tigania East District and the knowledge will be vital to all school administrators in Tigania East District and other Kenyan schools.

3.4 Drug Policy in Kenya

Drug abuse has permeated all strata of society with the youth and young adult being the category most affected. Most drug abusers fall between 16-30 years of age although experimentation begins much earlier. When these young people indulge in drug abuse at this early stage, their future is bleak and so is the country's.

As a result the government of Kenya ratified the United Nations conventions of Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic substance abuse and formed a special anti-narcotic unit within the police force and also enacted a law, "The Narcotic Drugs and Substance Control Act" (1994), to curb drug abuse and trafficking.

The drug policy in Kenya is very clear, that whoever possess, traffic, use, handle, cultivate, produce, distribute, manufacture or have possession of instruments used in or in connection with use of drugs will have committed criminal offence and may face up

to 20 years imprisonment or a fine of up to one Million. Also under the liquor and licensing Act it is an offence to sell alcohol to anyone less than 18 years of age.

On miraa, there is no clear policy. In 1934 Meru local native council prohibited use of miraa by people other than the Meru elders. In 1939, limited control measures on miraa were introduced by British Colonial government but were not enforced.

In 1951, miraa prohibitive ordinance (Cap 339, laws of Kenya) was introduced to miraa and applied to cultivation and possession of miraa. It was revised in 1974 through Presidential decree which only stated that an exporter of miraa must ensure that the receiving country has not banned miraa as a drug.

To-date, there is no clear cut policy on miraa chewing in Kenya. Since miraa is becoming a menace among the youth and students in particular, the researcher endeavours to find if there are effective school policies on drugs in line with Government policy on drugs. It is important to enforce rules and regulations in our secondary schools in order to address issues of drugs among students to avoid bleak future for our country Kenya.

Lack of research data linking miraa chewing to indiscipline cases in secondary schools, triggered the researcher to look into miraa chewing among students in day secondary schools in Tigania East District and its effects on discipline management thus filling this literature gap which will generate useful knowledge to school managers and other stakeholders in education sector.

3.5 Summary of Literature Review

The literature review has undertaken to look into the rationale for having disciplined students in our schools. It has looked into the use of other drugs e.g. alcohol, smoking, bhang which are commonly used by students in secondary schools thus leading to indiscipline. The review has looked at miraa and the literature only points at its effects on the chewer. Literature on its effects on school discipline is lacking.

This is the gap the researcher is out to address and show the effects of miraa chewing among students on discipline management in our schools.

Also, from literature review, there is clear Government policy on drugs. The researcher endeavors to find out how effective the school policies on Drugs in day secondary schools in Tigania East District are.

4. Methodology

4.1 Research Design

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The design was considered appropriate for the study because it would lead to a structure of investigations so as to obtain answers to research questions. According to Orodho (2003), survey design is highly applied in research because it generates answers to research questions. Ng'ang'a *et. Al* (2009) agrees that research design sets up a framework for adequate tests of the relations among variables thus generating basis for decisions and solutions. Therefore descriptive survey design fitted this study because the researcher wanted to describe the state of discipline in secondary schools in Tigania East District from the effects of miraa chewing among students.

The researcher used both qualitative and quantitative approaches where interview schedules were administered to principals and questionnaires to guidance and counseling teachers and students. Both closed - ended and open – ended questions were crafted in the questionnaires to give an opportunity to the respondents to express their views.

4.2 Locale of the Study

The study was carried out in Tigania East District which is in Meru County, Kenya. The researcher chooses the locale because it was easily accessible to the researcher and no similar study in the district had been conducted. There were 26 day secondary schools out of which 10 schools were randomly selected for this study.

4.3 Target Population

The study targeted 2000 boys from 26 day secondary schools in the district. Generally, the social cultural setting in Tigania Community does not allow girls/women to chew miraa. For this reason, girls were not involved in this study. Since the researcher will not be able to access all day secondary schools in Tigania East District due to financial implications only a manageable accessible population of 15% will be used for this study to represent the target population of 2000boys.

4.4 Sampling Techniques and Sample Size

Ng'ang'a *et al* (2009), defines sampling as taking any portion of a universe as representative of that population or universe. Out of 26 day schools, simple random sampling was used to select 10 day secondary schools in the district. Mugenda (2003)

asserts that the sampling techniques should ensure that samples are representative of whole population. Table 3.5.1 below presents the sample size for the study.

Table 2: Sample size of the study

School Type	Target population	Sample Percentage	Sample size
Mixed day schools	2000	15	300
Principal	26	40	10
Teachers	26	40	10
Total	2052		320

Source: Field data

4.5 Research Instrument

Two research instruments were used for this study. These are questionnaires which were administered to guidance and counseling teachers and students and interview schedules administered to principals. The questionnaire consisted of open-ended and closed-ended questions which generated quantitative data. Interview schedules containing specific themes generated qualitative data.

4.6 Piloting of Instruments

According to Orodho (2009), this is the most important stage in questionnaire design. It involves administration of questionnaire to a small representative sample identical to, but not included to the group you are going to survey to ensure that instruments of measurements are of acceptable reliability and validity. Through piloting, the researcher had an opportunity to make corrections to the instrument before proceeding with the study.

4.7 Reliability of a Research Instrument

Birkman (2001) defines reliability as the degree to which a score is stable and consistent when measured at different times, in different ways, or within different items within the same scale. Reliability of the research instruments in this study was determined through test-retest technique, where a questionnaire was given to a few identical subjects for the study.

The answered questionnaires were scored manually. The same process was repeated to the same group of subjects after a period of two weeks and answers were compared. Crombach Alpha coefficient correlation was used to determine reliability of the research instruments. A correlation of about 0.8 was considered high enough to accept the instrument as reliable for the study.

4.8 Validity of the Research Instruments

Kombo and Tromp (2005) defines validity as the degree to which results obtained from the analysis of the data actually represent the phenomenon under study, and is largely determined by the presence or absence of systematic error in data. Therefore, to test validity of the instruments used in their study, piloted questionnaire was revised to make it more valid and errors were corrected in the instrument.

4.9 Data Collection Procedure

The researcher got an introductory letter from the Ministry of Education with copies to the Meru County Director and District Education Officer, Tigania East District. Then on ethical ground the researcher sought permission from the principals of the schools to be involved in the study. Then the researcher conducted interview schedules to principals and administer questionnaires to teachers and students of the sampled school.

Respondents were assured of confidentiality.

4.10 Data Analysis Data Analysis

Once the questionnaires and interviews were administered, the mass of raw data collected was systematically organized in a manner that facilitated analysis. Themes of interview schedules were analyzed to give qualitative data. Closed-ended and open-ended questions in the questionnaires will require quantitative analysis where responses were assigned a number. For questions that require YES or NO response, the researcher assigned 1 to YES or 0 to NO. Uncompleted instruments were disregarded.

After all the responses from all the open-ended and closed-ended questions were scrutinized and coded, they were entered into the computer in preparation for analysis. To ensure uniform of questions coding in the questionnaire, a master codebook was used. For easy analysis, data processing was done using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (S.P.S.S). Analyzed data was presented inform of frequency distribution tables, graphs, Pie-charts and percentages.

5. Research Findings Presentation and Discussions

This chapter discusses the interpretation and presentation of the findings. The purpose of this study was to find out the effects of miraa chewing among students in day secondary schools in Tigania East District. It also sought to provide the way forward in order to curb miraa chewing menace among students. In particular, the following were the objectives of the study: to find out the effects of miraa chewing by students on discipline management in day secondary schools in Tigania East District, to investigate

indiscipline cases related to miraa chewing among students in Tigania East District, to find out measures employed by school management to curb miraa menace in day secondary schools in Tigania East District, to establish if there is effective drug policy in day secondary schools in Tigania East District and to identify strategies that could be used by school management to address miraa menace in day secondary schools in Tigania East District. The data collected was coded and entered in SPSS Package where analysis was done. Frequency tables, bar graphs and pie-charts were used to present the findings as per the research objectives upon which interpretations and conclusions were made.

5.1 Response Rate

The study sought to establish data from three hundred (300) students, ten (10) guidance and counseling masters/mistresses and ten (10) Principals as a representative sample. The cross sectional nature of the sample was intended to collect views regarding the subject from several perspectives as shown in the table below:

Table 3: Respondents

Group	Sample	Respondents	Percentage
Students	300	300	100
Guidance and Counseling Masters	10	9	90
Principal	10	10	100

5.2 Demographic Characteristics

This section presents the demographic characteristics of the sampled schools including principals, guidance and counseling masters/ mistresses and students. All the 300 boys involved in the study were from mixed day secondary schools.

Table 4: Students characteristics

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Form 1	40	13.3
Form 2	60	20
Form 3	100	33.3
Form 4	100	33.3
Total	300	

Out of the total of the students in the sampled schools, 13.3% were form ones, 20% were form twos, 33.3% were form threes and form fours respectively.

Table 5: Guidance and counseling masters/ mistresses profile

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	7	70
Female	2	20
Education level		
Diploma	2	20
Degree	7	70
Teaching Experience		
1-3 years	3	30
4-6 years	5	50
7 years and above	1	10

The above results shows 70% were males and 20% were females. In addition 70% were graduates and 20% Diploma holders. Further, 30% had teaching experience of between 1 and 3 years, 50% had experience of between 4 and 6 years and 10% had experience of more than 7 years.

Table 6: Principals profile

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	6	60
Female	4	40
Education level		
Diploma	0	0.0
Graduate	8	80
Masters	2	20
Headship Experience		
1year	0	0.0
2-4 years	3	30
5-7 years and above	7	70

The above table brings out the demographic characteristics of the principals from the schools sampled. According to results, 60% were males and 40% were females. In addition, 80% were graduates and 20% had masters. Further, 30% had headship experience of between 2 to 4 years while 70% had been head teachers for between 5 to 7 years.

5.3 Incidences of miraa chewing in day secondary schools in Tigania East District

To get a clear picture of miraa menace in day secondary schools in the district, the researcher sought to know if there were incidences of miraa chewing among students.

Responses were got from principals, guidance and counseling masters/mistresses and students. According to results from all the interviewed principals, 100% reported that there were very high cases of miraa chewing among students. Further, 90% of the guidance and counseling masters/mistresses reported there were very high cases of miraa chewing among students.

Table 7: Principals, guidance, and counseling masters/mistresses response on incidences of Miraa chewing among students

Respondents	Very high	High	Low	Percentage
Principals	10	0	0	100
Guidance and Counseling masters	9	0	0	90

Further, the researcher sought to establish the frequency of incidences of miraa chewing among students from form one (1) to form four (4). Data was captured according to age because in day secondary schools, there were older students of up to twenty five (25) years. From the results it was evident that younger students from age 13-14 had little knowledge on whether there were incidences of miraa chewing by the students. But as students advance in age in forms three and four, they fully indulge in miraa chewing and were aware of its effects. From the findings, 26% noted there were high incidences of miraa chewing, 6% noted very high incidences, 64% noted low incidences and 4% cited no incidences.

Possibly, the students concealed the truth of miraa chewing incidences due to fear of being associated with the vice and the effects it has on their lives. Though students did not come out clearly to expose miraa menace in day secondary schools in the district, probably due to fear, it was a clear indication that there were rampant cases of miraa chewing in day secondary schools in Tigania East District. As a result of this, students steal from others in order to get money to buy miraa, they sneak out of school in search of miraa, they defy authority, they bully others and lack concentration in class. Therefore, students who are miraa chewers are always on punishment thus affecting the smooth running of the school in terms of discipline management.

Table 8: Students' response on incidences of Miraa chewing

Age	High	Very High	Low	No Incidences	Total
13	0	0	17	0	7
14	2	1	19	0	18
15	1	5	24	0	30
16	13	0	19	4	30
17	20	5	29	2	56
18	17	1	50	5	109

19	17	2	17	2	36
20	9	2	13	0	9
24	0	0	4	0	4
25	0	3	0	0	3
Total	79	19	192	13	300
%	26	6	64	4	100

5.4 Effects of Miraa chewing on discipline management

The first objective sought to find out the effects of miraa chewing by students on discipline management in day secondary schools in Tigania East District. Bezuldenhout (2004) says that drugs can affect students-parents attachment leading to indiscipline issues such as poor concentration in class work activities, bullying others, sneaking out of school and lack of commitment in class work activities. United Nations (1992), says miraa users like other people seek approval for their behaviour from peer whom they attempt to convince to join them in their indiscipline behaviour such as theft, sneaking out of school and bullying as a way of seeking acceptance. Kaguthi, NACADA director (2004), while talking on the effects of drugs on school discipline he said that alcohol, cigarettes smoking and miraa chewing which are made available to students have affected discipline management in schools leading to strikes. Siele (in daily Nation, July 2005), maintains that the problem of drug abuse has continued to affect discipline management in schools because students sneak out of school in search of drugs and when they return they defy authority and start plotting a strike.

The research findings are in agreement because, according to the results, 45% of the students cited lack of sleep during the night and are sleepy in class hence are punished, 16% indicated sneaking out of school in search of miraa, 29% lack concentration in class and are not active hence are thrown out of class by teachers and 4% indicated bullying which is a serious indiscipline in secondary schools as it results to frequent fighting among students. These errant behaviours affect discipline management in day secondary schools because the school management constantly keeps on following students who are miraa chewers for punishment.

Figure 2: Effects of Miraa chewing

Further 60% of guidance and counseling masters/mistresses cited sleeping in class as one of the serious effects of miraa thus putting those students who chew miraa on punishment repeatedly, 20% cited theft cases where students steal other students items e.g. calculators to sell and get money to buy miraa and 30% cited bullying of other students. These behaviours constantly put the students on punishment thus affecting the smooth running of the school programmes.

Figure 3: Teachers' response on effects of Miraa chewing by students

NACADA (2010) asserts that upon chewing miraa, one loses concentration and cannot perform simple tasks, one develops antagonistic attitude to authority and bully others. When students chew miraa they display these indiscipline behaviours hence affecting discipline management in the school since both the teacher on duty and the deputy principal are always in pursuit of these errand students for punishment. Further, according to results from all the interviewed principals, 40% cited sneaking of students

out of school in search of miraa, 20% noted that students who chew miraa are so untidy and don't clean their uniform, 60% cited lack of appetite to students due to mouth sores which develop due to prolonged period of chewing miraa, 40% noted that students who chew miraa had poor health because they are poor feeders and are undisciplined because they are mostly on punishment and 60% cited absenteeism from school due to hangovers after chewing miraa for longer period during the night.

Figure 4: Principal's response on effects of miraa chewing by students

5.5 Indiscipline Cases Related to Miraa Chewing by Students.

This study objective was to find out indiscipline cases which are related to miraa chewing by students. According to the result, 31% of the students indicated that students sneak out of school to search for miraa in the neighbourhood. This leads to absenteeism from class, 19%.indicated that students lack concentration in class thus don't participate in class activities. This triggers the classroom teacher to throw such students out of class for punishment, 17% cited theft of other students property to sell and get money to buy miraa and 15% indicated that students who chew miraa bully others in school.

Figure 5: Indiscipline cases related to Miraa chewing as reported by students

Datta (1987) says that drugs such as alcohol, miraa chewing and marijuana when taken by student's triggers indiscipline behaviours such as protest against authority, sneaking out of school, bullying and organizing strikes.

Further according to guidance and counseling masters/ mistresses on indiscipline cases related to miraa, 40% pinpointed that students lack co-ordination in class such that they cannot perform simple tasks, 30% do not do their assignments hence are punished, 20% indicated that students who chew miraa are aggressive and bully other students in school and 10% cited that there were cases of theft where students steal items like calculators to sell and get money to buy miraa and other drugs such as alcohol and smoking respectively.

Figure 6: Teachers' opinion on Indiscipline cases related to Miraa chewing by students

All the interviewed principals cited sneaking out of school as the most common indiscipline case related to miraa chewing. It was evident that the indiscipline cases cited by the students were in one way or another cited by the guidance and counseling masters/mistresses and the principals. This pointed clearly, that principals should strengthen rules and regulations to deal with indiscipline cases related to miraa chewing by students and ensuring everybody in the community is brought on board in tackling miraa chewing by students.

5.6 Measures Employed by School Management to Curb Miraa Chewing Menace among Students

This objective sought to find out disciplinary measures enforced by school management to curb miraa chewing menace among students. According to the results, 71% of the students cited guidance and counseling as the best method to deal with indiscipline cases related to miraa chewing, 11% suspension, 9% advocated expulsion, 7% advocated no punishment and 1% cited manual work and none advocated canning.

Table 9: Students’ response on how to deal with indiscipline cases related to Miraa chewing

Age	Canning	Expulsion	G&C	Manual Work	Suspension	No Punishment	Total
13	0	0	4	4	4	0	12
14	0	8	10	0	4	0	22
15	0	0	20	0	4	4	28
16	0	8	30	0	4	4	46
17	0	8	50	0	0	0	58
18	0	0	60	0	10	10	80
19	0	0	10	0	8	4	22
20	0	4	12	0	0	0	16
24	0	0	8	0	0	0	8
25	0	0	8	0	0	0	8
Total	0	28	212	4	34	22	300
Percentage	0%	9%	71%	1%	11%	7%	100%

Further according to guidance and counseling masters/mistresses, 80% cited guidance and counseling as the best corrective method to address miraa chewing among students by inviting external speakers to speak against the vice, strength peer counseling group in school and inviting the clergy for spiritual guidance, 70% advocated punishment of students who engage in miraa chewing, 20% cited strengthening of school rules and regulations and involving parents in guiding their children respectively.

Figure 7: Teachers’ suggestions on ways to deal with indiscipline from Miraa chewing

Bishop Nzimbi (2004), emphasized that churches should organize guidance and counseling programmes on drug abuse to schools, colleges and universities and spiritual crusades to fight drug abuse in schools and colleges.

Githinji (2004) supports this idea by saying that churches should establish rehabilitation centers to offer counseling to drug abusers and offer both physical and inner healing to drug abusers and addicts.

Further according to all the interviewed principals, 100% advocated strict discipline where all the teachers are involved in tracking the students behaviour from morning until they leave school in the evening, 80% cited guidance and counseling to errand students in order to help them leave the habit and 60% advocated strengthening of school rules and regulations and policies on drugs in day schools.

Figure 8: Principals' opinion on interventions to Miraa chewing

While addressing the Third Global Youth Employment Summit, His Excellency Hon. Mwai Kibaki (Daily Nation 13th September 2006), reported that since youth today are faced with the challenges of drug abuse, there should be awareness programmes to guide and counsel them to avoid risky behaviours associated with drug abuse.

Kombo (2005), agrees that strict discipline is very importance in dealing with drug abuse in schools for effective learning and if not enforced by the management; the school cannot achieve their set goals and objectives. Okumbe (1998), agrees that school discipline is paramount and should therefore be used to modify the behaviour of students who engage in drug taking and discourage others from involvement of taking such drugs.

Therefore, the school management should ensure there are elaborate discipline mechanisms and functional guidance and counseling departments to guide students for the school to achieve its goals and objectives.

5.7 Effectiveness of Drug Policies in Day Secondary School in Tigania East District

This objective sought to find out if there were effective drug policies in day secondary schools in Tigania East District. According to students response, 62% indicated there were drug policies in schools. Further 38% of the students indicated that they were not aware of the policy.

Table 10: Students' response on if there is a drug policy in school

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	186	62%
No	114	38%

Source: Field data

Hawkins (1988) agrees that school policies on drugs are important and lack of clear drug policies contributes a lot to drug abuse by students leading to indiscipline. Further, the researcher sought to establish the effectiveness of drug policy from students. Effectiveness is the degree to which students uphold and feel the effect of the policy in relation to their errant behaviour. From the results, 27% said that the policy was effective, 34% said the policy was not effective and 39% of the students did not respond to the question.

Table 11: Students' response on effectiveness of drug policy

Form	Effective	Not Effective	No Response
1	13	16	30
2	5	15	14
3	25	21	35
4	37	50	39
Total	80	102	118

Source: Field data

Further according to the guidance and counseling master/ mistresses response on the effective of the drug policy in schools, 45% indicated that there was effective policy, 44% cited that it was moderately effectives and 11% indicated that the drug policy in day schools was not effective and requires the school administration to intervene. For the school programmes to run smoothly, there must be elaborate drug policies to ensure good students discipline.

Figure 9: Teacher’s opinion on effectiveness of drug policy in schools

Further, the researcher sought to establish the effectiveness of the drug policy in day schools by interviewing principals. In their response, they said that it was a big challenge to effectively implement the policy particularly in a society where miraa acts as the main source of income to pay fees and feed the families. Also the society and the clergy does not speak against miraa as a drug thus students finding miraa chewing as a way of life. But there should be effective drug policies to safeguard students and ensure good discipline in day schools.

At National level, the government of Kenya enacted a law, “The Narcotics Drugs and Substance Control Act” (1994), to curb drug abuse and trafficking. The policy is clear that whoever possess, traffic, use, handle, cultivate, produce, distribute, manufacture or have possession of instruments used in or in connection with use of drugs will have committed criminal offence and may face up to 20 years imprisonment or a fine of up to one million. Also, the government of Kenya has put in place some other policy measures to address drugs problem. Ngilu (2006), as Minister of Health banned cigarettes smoking, brewing of “changaa” and “Kumi-Kumi” to safeguard the Kenya citizens from taking drugs. Therefore, school principals should ensure there are drug policies in their schools to ensure free drugs environment thus good discipline among students.

5.8 Strategies to Curb Miraa Chewing by Students in Day Secondary Schools in Tigania East District

This objective sought to identify strategies/ solutions to curb miraa chewing among students. From the respondents, guidance and counseling was the most advocated strategy to curb miraa chewing among students. Guidance and counseling is the process of helping individuals to understand themselves by discovering their own

needs, interests and capabilities in order to formulate their own goals and make plans for realizing those goals. This strategy is highly advocated by counselors because they employ it to correct unlike behaviours among individuals. Nzimbi (2004), emphasized guidance and counseling programmes to the youth to enlighten them on the effects of drugs taking. Mwana „a“ Nzeki (1999), agrees that there should be guidance and counseling and spiritual nourishment to the youth in our Kenyan schools who are faced with the challenges of drug abuse. From the research findings, it was evident that majority of the students (71%) advocated guidance and counseling as the best solution in dealing with miraa chewing menace. Through suspension, one is withdrawn from his peer and throughout the suspended period the individual tries to get rid of bad behaviour. A section of the students (11%) advocated suspension and all the respondents were against canning. Kenya (2001), through a gazette notice No. 56 of 2001, banned canning in schools thus canning is not the best approach to instill discipline.

Further, according to the findings, 45% of the guidance and counseling masters /mistress advocated guidance and counseling, 35% were for the opinion that community should be involved in counseling their children on the effects of miraa chewing and 20% advocated punishment.

Figure 10: Possible solutions to curb Miraa chewing by students as reported by teachers

Further findings revealed that 100% of the interviewed principals advocated strict discipline where students must adhere to school rules and regulations to avoid being punished, and 80% advocated guidance and counseling. Therefore, based on the findings above, the issue of miraa chewing has contributed a lot to indiscipline in day secondary schools in Tigania East District, thus posing great challenge to discipline management and school administrations should ensure there are elaborate rules and regulations in order to maintain high discipline in day schools in the District. In my

opinion, I strongly recommend guidance and counseling as the best strategy to curb miraa chewing among students because it is the bedrock process of correcting an individual with maladjusted behaviour thus discarding the negative behaviour and embracing positive leaving which is more fulfilling in life.

6. Summary of the Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations

This chapter presents the summary of the findings of the study. The purpose of the study was to find out the effects of miraa chewing by students on discipline management in day secondary schools in Tigania East District and make the necessary recommendations. In addition, it sought to analyse indiscipline cases related to miraa chewing and measures employed by the school administration to curb the menace. Finally, the study sought to establish if there were effective drug policies in schools and come up with strategies aimed at curbing miraa chewing by students in the District.

6.1 Summary of the Findings

The study targeted three hundred (300) students, ten (10) guidance and counseling masters and ten (10) principals from the 10 sampled secondary schools in Tigania East District. The response rate was over 90% in the targeted schools. The study also established that in some day schools, there were older students of up to 25 years. In addition, all the sampled schools had a principal and guidance and counseling master.

The first objective of the study was to establish the effects of miraa chewing on discipline management in Day Secondary Schools in Tigania East District. The study revealed that sneaking out of school, theft, lack of concentration and bullying were the main effects of miraa chewing. These affected discipline management because cases of theft were rampant and the administration had difficulty in following theft cases among students. Student's absenteeism was also common as they sneaked out of school in search of miraa. Also, there were cases of bullying among students resulting to frequent fights thus affecting the smooth running of the school since a lot of attention was on discipline management. Bezuldenhout (2004), says that drugs can affect students – parents attachment leading to poor concentration in class, bullying others, sneaking out of school and lack commitment in class work activities. NACADA (2010) says that miraa chewers lack concentration, bully others and defy authority.

The second study objective sought to establish indiscipline cases related to miraa chewing by students. The study established that sneaking out of school, lack of concentration, theft, disobedience to authority; aggression and uncleanliness were the

common indiscipline cases. These findings were in agreement from all categories of respondents.

The third objective sought to establish the measures employed by school management to curb miraa chewing menace among students. The study revealed that guidance and counseling was the most preferred method of dealing with miraa chewing culprits. Other alternatives according to the study were punishment, suspension, expulsion and manual work. From the findings, students were against canning of deviant students.

The fourth objective sought to establish the effectiveness of drug policies in day secondary schools in Tigania East District. According to the responses from students, guidance and counseling masters/ mistresses and principals, there were drug policies in day schools in the district but were not effectively enforced by the school administration.

The last objective sought to identify strategies to curb miraa chewing by students in day school in the district. The findings of the study revealed that guidance and counseling was the most preferred strategy to get rid of miraa chewing menace among students in day Secondary schools in the district.

6.2 Conclusion

Based on the objectives and findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn: Firstly, there were varied effects of miraa chewing on students. Theft cases were common and school managements were oftenly following up theft cases. Sneaking out of school was common leading to student's absenteeism. Bullying of others resulted to frequent fighting in the school among students. These errand behaviours affected discipline management in day schools. Secondly, there were rampant cases of miraa chewing among students in day secondary schools in the district. Thirdly, the most preferred method of dealing with undisciplined students who chew miraa was guidance and counseling. Fourthly, it was evident from the findings that there were drug policies in day schools in the district but was not effective because the school administrations were not enforcing them fully. Finally, the study established that, guidance and counseling was the most favoured strategy to deal with miraa menace because 71% of the students preferred guidance and counseling, 80% guidance and counseling masters/ mistresses and principals respectively advocated guidance and counseling. Therefore, the study concludes that miraa chewing menace is rampant in day secondary schools in Tigania East District because the school administrations are not keen in enforcing drug policies effectively to ensure drug free environments.

6.3 Recommendations of the Study

Based on the conclusions above, the following recommendations were drawn:

First, the government of Kenya through the Ministry of Education should provide trained guidance and counseling teachers or in-service those who are untrained to be able to guide students appropriately.

Secondly, the schools should work in collaboration with the parents, the clergy and the local administration to address miraa chewing menace among students in day secondary schools in the District.

Third, the school administrations should ensure that the drug policy in school is clearly understood by all the students and the consequences to the culprits.

Fourth, teachers and parents should desist from chewing miraa openly and instead they should be good role models to students. Finally, the Ministry of Education should come up with policy guideline to curb miraa chewing by students in areas where the crop is grown so as to enhance accessibility, Equity and retention of students in our schools.

6.4 Suggestions for further studies

1. The study restricted itself to the effects of miraa chewing by students on discipline management. There is need for a study to look at drop-out rate from school due to miraa chewing.
2. There is need for a study to look at the effects of miraa chewing by students on academic performance.
3. There is need for a study to investigate if miraa chewing among the youth has contributed to low enrolment of boy child in day secondary schools in comparison with enrolment of girl child in the District.

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